

Research Article

Religion Education as an Instrument for Prevention and Control of Crimes in Nigerian Universities**Obilom J.E.C¹, Mbah Lucy Ucha² and Goshwe Simi, Angela²****¹Faculty of Education, University of Jos Plateau State Nigeria****²Plateau Private School, Jos Plateau State.*****Abstract***

The paper examined the role of religion education as an instrument for prevention and control of crime in Nigerian Universities. The purpose was to determine how the teaching of religion in universities could help to prevent and control crimes. The study was necessitated by the high rate of crime prevalent in universities and the bid to seek for lasting remedy. The study raised three research questions and two hypotheses. Descriptive survey was adopted for the study. The sample for the study consisted of 145 respondents (120 students and 25 lecturers) drawn from Faculties of Education of University of Jos and Plateau State University, Bokokos. The convenience sampling technique was used to draw up the sample. A structured self-made questionnaire was used for data collection and was tagged Religion Education and Crime Prevention and Control Questionnaire (REACPCQ). The instrument (REACPCQ) was validated by two senior lecturers from Faculty of Education, University of Jos. The test-retest reliability coefficient of the instrument obtained using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation method was 0.79. The percentage and the Chi-square were the statistical techniques used for data analysis. Results showed that factors that dispose students to crime include non-functional education system, faulty home background, academic frustration, poor students' welfare services among others. The opinions of students and lecturers regarding causes of crime among university students were found to be different. Also, a significant effect of religion on crime prevention and control was found. The study recommended among other things that university authorities should improve on the social and academic welfare of students. Religion education should be encouraged in universities. The study therefore concludes that religion education is necessary for preventing and controlling crimes among students in the university.

Keywords: Religion education, crime, prevention, control

Received: 10 Feb. 2017

Accepted: 28 July 2017

Introduction

Religion has played particularly important roles in ethical philosophy down the ages. This is because it has been a useful instrument for moral codes of conduct. The level of morality in the nation today has gone so low that every well-meaning Nigerian is forced to ask the question what has gone wrong? Where are we going to? The high level of immoral behaviour observed among citizens especially the youth in our nation calls for great concern. There is a litany of evils present in our nation. Some of them include, bribery, corruption, armed robbery, prostitution, cultism, rape, killing and child trafficking. Above all, there is great devaluation of human life. Killing of people has become a "norm" in the society. The high level of immorality in the country is captured by Gotan (1992) when he stated thus:

Moral integrity is going down through bribery and corruption, nepotism, organized robbery, violence, forgeries in financial institutions and examination malpractices in schools. Universal indiscipline has become conspicuous in national life. A materialistic outlook is permeating national life, showing itself in cheatings, hoarding and selfishness, while the nation as a whole continues to be poorly fed, badly housed, raggedly clothed and ridden with diseases (pg 2)'.

Further more, Nduka (1993) concurs Gotan (1992) when he documented thus:

...Nigeria in its third decade of independence is in a state of moral crises – a deepening crises which pervades every aspect of our national life..., there is lack of discipline in schools, including students, rioting, fraud of varying degrees and magnitudes, examination misconducts, drug abuse, forgery, which are a reflection of a slow and steady drift to moral bankruptcy (p.23)

At present, Nigeria has acquired the indelible reputation of a country that is blatantly corrupt and whose officials have little concern for accountability, probity and transparency. The situation is so bad that no sector of the economy is spared. Every fact of the society including education sector is plagued with this virus of moral decadence. Education is a means of shaping character and moulding lives for meaningful living in the society. In the same vein, religion education is meant to teach young people how to love God and respect mankind among other things. The study is set to examine how religion education can help prevent and control crimes among students in Nigerian universities.

Statement of the Problem

The present state of high level of crime in Nigeria motivated the study. There is an ever-increasing crime rate permeating the society and perpetrated mostly by youth. There is

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4181 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

hardly any day that passes without the mass media carrying one report or the other about such crimes. Several efforts made in recent past to check-mate crimes in universities include expulsion of students, suspension of erring students, police intervention. However, these efforts have not yielded the desired results as there is still persistent increase in crime in Nigeria universities.

The problem of this study is embedded in this broad question “how can religion education help to prevent and control crimes in Nigerian universities.

Purpose of the Study

The study is designed to achieve the following objectives to:

1. Identify factors that predispose students to crime.
2. Examine how students’ involvement in crime affect the administration of universities.
3. Examine the contribution of Religion Education in the prevention and control of crime.
4. Compare the opinions of students and lecturers regarding factors that predispose students to crime.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions.

1. What are the causes of crime among students in Nigeria universities?
2. How does students’ involvement in crimes affect the management of Universities?
3. In what ways can Religion Education help in preventing and controlling crimes in Nigeria Universities?

Hypotheses

The hypotheses below are formulated for the study.

1. There is no significant difference between the opinions of lecturers and students regarding causes of crime among students in Nigeria universities.
2. There is no significant effect of religion education on crime prevention and control in Nigerian Universities.

Methods and Procedure

The study adopted a survey design, specifically the cross-sectional survey. The population for the study consisted of all the lecturers and students in the Faculties of Education of University of Jos and Plateau State University Bokokos. The sample for the study is made up of 145 respondents consisting of 120 undergraduate students and 25 Lecturers drawn from the two universities. The convenience sampling method was used to draw the sample. The reason was that only those students and lecturers who are conveniently available and willing to participate in the study were used for the study.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire tagged Religion Education and Crime Prevention and Control Questionnaire (REACPCQ). The questionnaire was validated by two experts from Faculty of Education, University of Jos, Nigeria. The reliability coefficient of the

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4181 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

instrument was 0.79. Personal contact method was adopted in collecting data for the study. The study used the percentage and the chi-square to analyze data for the study for the research questions and hypotheses respectively.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the causes of crime among students in Nigerian Universities?

Table 1: Causes of Crime among Nigeria Universities' Students

S/No	Statement	Agreed		Disagreed	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1.	Faulty home background	132	93.1	10	6.9
2.	Poor social values	128	88.3	17	11.7
3.	Poor Students Welfare	132	91.0	13	9.0
4.	Non-functional education system	140	96.6	05	3.4
5.	Academic Frustration	138	95.2	07	4.8
6.	Poverty	139	95.9	06	4.1
7.	Poor learning environment	119	82.1	26	17.9

Table 1 shows that nonfunctional education system (96.6%), poverty (95.9%) faulty home background (93.1%) are lead causes of crime among Nigerian students in the universities.

Research Question 2: How does students' involvement in crimes affect the management of universities?

Table 2: Effects of students' Involvement in Crimes on Management of Universities

S/No	Statement	Agreed		Disagreed	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1.	Crime involvement hinders attendance to lecture	130	89.7	15	10.3
2.	Students are suspended leading to truncation of their educational career	140	96.6	05	3.4
3.	Sometimes the Institution is closed down causing delay in graduation	139	95.9	06	4.1
4.	It can lead to death of lecturers and students through riots	142	97.9	03	2.1
5.	Some indicted lecturers are sometimes sacked leading to shortage of staff	138	95.2	07	4.8
6.	Poverty	139	95.9	06	4.1
7.	Poor learning environment	119	82.1	26	17.9

Research Question 3

In what ways can religion education help in preventing and controlling crimes in Nigerian Universities?

Table 3: Role of Religion Education in Preventing and Controlling Crime in Nigerian Universities

S/No	Statement	Agreed Freq.	%	Disagreed Freq.	%
1.	Religion education emphasizes good morality	138	95.2	07	4.8
2.	Discipline and obedience to instruction are Integral aspects of Religion Education	140	96.6	05	3.4
3.	Religion Education teaches youths the fear of God	142	97.9	03	2.1
4.	Religion Education exposes students to right Ways of life.	144	99.3	01	0.7
5.	Religion Education teaches students the consequences of bad behavior	143	98.6	02	1.4

Result in Table 3 reveals that Religion Education exposes students to right ways of life (99.3%) and also teaches students the consequences of bad behavior (98.6%) among others.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean opinions of lecturers and students regarding causes of crime among students in Nigeria universities.

Table 4: Chi-square Summary of the Difference in Opinions of Students and Lecturers regarding Causes of Crime

Status	Agreed Fo (fe)	Disagreed Fo(fe)	N	χ^2 tab	χ^2 cal	Remark
Lecturers	15 (19.8)	10(5.2)	25	3.84	6.766	Reject
Students	100 (95.2)	20(24.8)	120			Ho
Total	115	30	145			

From Table 4, the χ^2 calculated is greater than χ^2 table, that is $6.777 > 3.84$ at df of 1 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference between the mean opinions of students and lecturers on the causes of crimes among students in Nigerian Universities.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
 ISSN: 2141 - 4181 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant effect of religion education on the prevention and control of crimes among students in Nigerian Universities.

Table 5: Chi-square Summary of the Effect of Religion Education on Crime Prevention and Control

Variables	Fo	fe	(fo - fe) ²	(fo - fe) ² fe	χ^2 cal	χ^2 tab	Remark
Religion Education.	115	72.5	1806.25	2.491	5.982	3.84	Reject Ho
Crime Prevention & Control	10	72.5	1806.25	2.491	$\sum \chi^2 = 5.982$		

Evidences in Table 5 shows that calculated χ^2 value (5.982) is greater than χ^2 table of 3.84 at degree of freedom (df) 1 at 5% level of significance hence there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This leads to a conclusion that there is a significant effect of religion education on crime prevention and control in Nigerian Universities.

Discussion

The result of research question one showed that the lead factors that predispose students to crime in Nigeria Universities are non-functional education system, academic frustration and faulty home background because the home is a critical factor regarding the training of students/children. The home is the child's first place of contact in the world. Again, the education system is equally important in the lives of students. School as an agent of socialization, is a place where responsible citizens are raised. When the education system is not functioning well due to some lapses, students are prone to crimes (Haggai 2004). Regarding academic frustrations, Omale (2010) observed that many students are faced with a lot of challenges. When students face academic frustration, they tend to engage in some forms of examination malpractice in order to pass examinations. Some students have been victimized by lecturers and have been failed in some courses by the same lecturers. Repetition of such incidences can lead to frustration on the part of the affected students which can dispose them to crimes.

The involvement of students in crime affects the management of the universities by causing death of students and lecturers. Maduabum (2008) was of the view that when students engage in some crimes as rampage or occultism most times they could be deadly, a lot of lives are lost in addition to destruction of properties. In each of these

situations, academic activities are truncated. It is even worse in serious cases where the affected institution is closed down for some time. The closure causes delay in graduation of students and delay in completion of the prescribed body of knowledge to the students. Religion Education was found to be of importance in curbing crimes. This is because religion education teaches people fear of God and respect for mankind. The high rate of crimes in Nigeria has been attributed to lack of fear of God. Obilom (2003) noted that most young people lack the fear of God hence they engage in all kinds of evil to the detriment of themselves. Religion education is a potent instrument that could be utilized to reduce the rate of crimes among students by inculcating the fear of God in young learners.

The opinions of lecturers and students regarding the causes of crimes among students differed. This may be due to differences in level of education, reasoning and maturation of lecturers and students. As Okeke (2004) noted that one's experiences in life, exposure and level of education can cause disparity between him and another person. It is clear that students and lecturers may have different orientations regarding the problem being investigated, hence the result.

It was gathered that religion education has significant effect on crime prevention and control. This result is not surprising because Megawanyi (2003) documented that one of the objectives of religion education is to inculcate in learners moral values and the fear of God. The fear of God is the beginning of wisdom, and departure from evil. When youths (students) are groomed in the fear of God, their tendency to crime will be drowned.

Summary of Findings

The following findings were made from the study:

1. Factors that predispose students to crime include non-functional education system, faulty home background, and academic frustration among others.
2. Students' involvement in crime hinders effective management of universities by causing death of students and lecturers etc.
3. Religion education helps in preventing and controlling crime by teaching youths the fear of God, discipline etc.
4. The mean opinions of students and lecturers regarding causes of crimes among students were found to be significantly different.

5. There is a significant effect of religion education on the prevention and reduction of crimes among students in Nigerian Universities.

Conclusion

The study investigated the role of religion education in preventing and controlling crimes in Nigerian universities. It was gathered that non-functional education system, faulty home background, academic frustrations dispose students to crimes. The involvement of students in crime affects the management of universities. Religion education was seen to have great roles to play in preventing and controlling crimes. Students and lecturers opinions regarding the causes of crimes were found to differ. The study therefore concludes that there is a significant effect of religion education on prevention and control of crimes in Nigerian universities.

Recommendations

The following were recommended:

1. The government should ensure that education system is made functional to address the needs of the students.
2. Parents should ensure that the home background is good to be able to raise responsible citizens.
3. University authorities should endeavor to see to the improvement of the welfare of students to avoid discouragement.
4. Academic counseling should be regularly organized for students to reduce academic frustration.
5. Religion education should be encouraged at all levels of education by inculcating it into the general studies curriculum.

References

- Gotan C. T. (1992). A summative evaluation of the objectives of the implemented junior secondary school Christian Religion education curriculum in the Middle Belt. Unpublished Ph.D Dissertation Faculty of Education, Unijos.
- Haggai; M.P. (2004). *Child Psychology*. Jos Yabyangs Press.
- Maduabum, M.A. (2008). The role of the society in crime prevention. *Journal of Ethical Issues* 2(1), 71 - 80.
- Megawanyi U.O. (2003). The training of the child. Retrieved from www.childtraining.org.uk. Retrieved 25/6/15.
- Nduka, O. I.(1993). *New Perspective in Moral Education*. Ibadan: Evans Brothers (Nig) Ltd.
- Obilom, J.E.C. (2003). *The Christian Religion teaching the 21st Century*. Jos: Deka Publication.
- Okeke, O.S. (2004). Morality and character formation. In J.S. Benega (Ed). *Moral characters and Civil Education in Elementary Schools*, 131 - 138.
- Omale, E.M, (2012). Emerging Issues about Morality. *Review of Educational Research* 2(3); 93 - 105.